

TEACHING IS ABOUT INSPIRATION, NOT INFORMATION**Sh. Mamitaliyeva**

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Abstract: Inspiration is the most important subject that should be under consideration in every field of education. Education is an incredible opportunity to open new world to each individuals. Obviously, educators play an important role in young generations’ life. That’s why teachers are mentioned as responsible people to any countries future position.

Keywords: Teachers, learner, golden strategies, curiosity.

Abstract: Qiziqish o’yg’otish ta’limning har bir sohasida ko’rib chiqilishi kerak bo’lgan eng muhim mavzulardan biridir. Talim har bir insonga yangi dunyo ochish uchun ajoyin imkoniyatdir. Albatta tarbiyalovchilar yosh avlodning hayotida muhim rol o’ynaydi. Shuning uchun ham o’qtuvchilar mamlakatning kelgusi mas’ul shaxs sifatida e’tirof e’tiladilar.

Калит сўзлар: педагог, ўқувчи, олтин қоидалар, қизиқиш.

Аннотация: Воодушевление – самый важный аспект, который должен рассматриваться во всех областях образования. Образование – это невероятная возможность открыть новый мир для каждого человека. Несомненно, педагоги играют важную роль в жизни молодого поколения. И поэтому, учителя считаются ответственными за будущее каждой страны.

Ключевые слова: Педагог, ученик, золотые стратегии, любознательность.

One of the most significant phases that every teacher must pay more attention is learning “How to motivate students”. It is an urgent side of becoming sufficiently teacher. Students who are not motivated will not catch up the content efficiently. They won’t receive information, they won’t take part in the lesson and some of them may even turn disintegrated. Learners may be not having interest in the topic because of various arguments: they may find that they can’t be involved in the matter, consider the strategy which is using for inspiring students to the lesson is un-engaging or be mentally confused by extrinsic factors. The best teachers usually have one thing in common. Students often say that their best teachers were ones who inspired them. Obviously, the kinds of teachers who will be kept in mind for a long time are capable of attracting learners to study. There are several ways to inspire students. Here are really useful seven tips that are called “7 Golden strategies”.

Giving specific direction Learning under right direction empowers students. When students know exactly what they must do to full tasks, they will close in their work with self-assurance and interest. Giving accurate direction is an art form that

requires specific ability. Keep them simple, brief and logical. Teaching and learning in an inspired class is like a having good time to both teacher and students. Obviously, there are such kind of students that have a desire to learn, and teacher need to give right direction to start. For example, mathematic first show the way of solving the equation then learners do it as the same as their teacher did but in another example. That is also give desire to continue the lesson to students.

Curiosity One more helpful trigger to being inspired is curiosity. If students desired to find out more about a topic, they would solve challenging assignments in order to fulfill their curiosity. Indeed, asking more instigative questions that reinforce them to think widely, the more students can activate their curiosity. Attract all students to the lesson. For instance, if you are going over a reading in class, ask students to take turns reading sections out loud. Ending help to learners to summarize and analyze all information.

Working with some fun Great teacher organizes lessoning fun, as animating, inspiring lessons are crucial to a students’ academic success. Sometimes being on motivating teachers is more workable for students who are likely to hide their capability, shirk responsibility or disengagement. Thus creating your classroom an exhilarating atmosphere for learning will hold students’ captivation. They learn best when they are both challenged and interested further.

Using dissimilar materials Avoid teaching students an ordinary, simple-organized lesson. Decorate a lesson plan to make out all students. Try to use real examples, for the purpose of being easy to imagine the gist of the topic to learners. Find an association to students’ lives and make them interest to take part in an activities that are a bit pointed. Illustrating ideal things, events, and even heroes will be more involving rather than turning over the stuffy pages of the textbook during the whole lesson. Without any doubt, technology can be a useful way to wake up the inspiration of students. The main reason is that 21-century teenagers are interested in modern tools like computer, telephone, electronic boards and about. Moreover, the most of students think travel is pleasurable regardless of whether it is a training trip or for having a rest.

Paying attention to learning styles Use various teaching modals during the lesson owing to dissimilar learning ways students have. This means to have lessons that motivate participation with diverse senses. Make use of being visuals, permit students to partake in hands on exertions, and make the theme verbally. In fact, visual learner learn through images, needs and likes to visual things, kinesthetic learner wants to touch and feel the world around them, auditory learner has excellent memory for names, dates, and trivia, last logical learner enjoy strategy games, computers and experiments with a purpose. So be aware of them and use the tips to teach correctly. Usually giving choice to students may affect the balance of learning

and understanding sufficiently.

Praising and rewarding Most helpful trick to encourage students in any subjects is rewarding them. In addition, praising also help to improve self-confidence. When students know their teacher likes and believes them they work hard than before. Be a positive with learners’ behavior and fully questions. During the lesson try to praise them for even a little right answer. That is a key to enter the students’ inside not as a teacher but as a friend. Try to encourage your students by taking them out or go on field trips. Make a game like “who is the first” say some information that is connected to your last lesson about. For instance, in chemistry lesson teachers can ask “what is the season now?” yes this is super easy for students but then connect to your subject. Give following question “what kind of natural processes are appearing in the surrounding? And Why?” as we see All the thing is coming to the subject. At the end students enter the last lesson and teacher also know which student did and who didn’t repeat the lesson with help of entering question activity.

Loving what you do Don’t forget to find enjoyment and loving what you are doing. Those are really crucial points which anyone must grab attention in order to achieve success and satisfaction with their activities. This a piece of practical advice applies for everything in both academic and true life. Don’t forget that Great teachers are not remembered for only knowledge or experience but also the way they encourage and lift the students’ inspiration. Organizing captivating lesson can bring the highest level of satisfaction that he did the lesson sufficiently. Maybe you come across lots of difficulties during the lesson but don’t forget “Education is not the filling of a pail, but the lighting of a fair” as William Butler Yeats is quoted as saying. There is a single thing that inspire teachers is becoming an influence in students’ life by forging strong relationship.

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